

Start on Sustainability Starter Kit

6. ASSESSMENT AND PLANNING

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ABOUT OUR PROJECT

By implementing Start on Sustainability, we aim **to equip micro-enterprises** with the necessary **tools and resources** to take meaningful action towards sustainability, thereby contributing to a more sustainable and resilient EU economy.

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01

INTRODUCTION TO THE MODULE

01

OVERVIEW OF THE TOPIC

02

OBJECTIVES

03

LEARNING OUTCOMES

1. OVERVIEW

- A sustainable future is possible only when it is pursued with a sense of urgency. Corporate sustainability of micro-SMEs requires management, strategies and operations that ensure the transition to a sustainable future.
- This "Assessment and Planning" module provides answers to the new challenges and requirements that self-employed, entrepreneurs and micro-SMEs will face in order to grow in a sustainable way.
- The growing awareness and demand for greater commitment by companies to environmental conservation requires micro-SMEs in different sectors to start deepening their knowledge of the main concepts, applications, methodologies, tools and requirements that sustainability encompasses.
- They will have the opportunity to acquire knowledge about corporate sustainability, carbon footprint, circular economy, ESG, reporting, sustainable development goals and steps to follow to develop a Sustainability Plan.

02. OBJECTIVES

Overall Objective

To implement sustainable practices by micro-SMEs in their operations.

Specific Objectives

- Provide a comprehensive Methodology for sustainability plans, aligned with ESG (Environmental, Social and Governance) criteria.
- Raise awareness of the need for and benefits of strategic sustainability planning.
- Disseminate good practices on sustainable business management.
- To provide support for public initiatives and policies on sustainability in the European and Spanish context.

03. LEARNING OUTCOMES

- **Management commitment** to the Sustainability Strategy.
- The need to carry out a prior **self-diagnosis**.
- The importance of measuring sustainable management through **indicators** for the fulfilment of sustainability objectives.
- The value and influence of **stakeholders**.
- Evaluation, control and **monitoring** of the Micro-SMEs Sustainability Plan.

02

**SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS
OPERATIONS**

01

What is a Sustainability Plan and why is it Important?

02

Content of the Sustainability Plan

03

Legal and Reporting Obligations on Sustainability for Micro and SMEs

04

European-level Sustainability Certification or Advisory Bodies and Institutions

What is a Sustainability Plan and why is it Important?

- A roadmap of "clear, measurable and realistic targets to improve organisational sustainability" aligned with the SDG 2030.
- It engages all employees, managers, customers, suppliers and investors.
- *On an average, almost 8 out of 10 companies that developed a sustainability strategy/plan improved their environmental performance and their employee satisfaction levels, while more than 7 out of 10 saw improved customer satisfaction level.*

What is a Sustainability Plan and why is it Important?

Benefits of implementing the Sustainability Plan for Micro-SMEs.

- Improved corporate image and brand reputation.
- Attracting investors.
- Reduction of operating costs.

What is a Sustainability Plan and why is it Important?

- Access to public funds: grants, subsidies, public sector contracts.
 - Since 2013, aid for the environment and energy efficiency in the EU has increased fivefold.

In 2021 they accounted for 55% of the total.

Evolution of aid for the environment and energy efficiency in the EU up to 2021 - source: *Informe Anual de Ayudas Públicas* (page 28). Comisión Nacional de los Mercados y de la Competencia. 14 de noviembre de 2023. IAP/CNMC/001/23.

Breakdown of horizontal (non-sectoral) aid by objective in the EU in 2021 - source: *Informe Anual de Ayudas Públicas* (page 28). Comisión Nacional de los Mercados y de la Competencia. 14 de noviembre de 2023. IAP/CNMC/001/23.

What is a Sustainability Plan and why is it Important?

Legal and reporting obligations on sustainability for micro-SMEs

- Sustainability reporting will be mandatory for micro-enterprises from 2027, which may opt out of the regulation until 1 January 2028, when they will be required to report on sustainability issues for financial years starting on or after 1 January 2026 (Directive (EU) 2022/2464 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 (CSRD)).
- The sustainability report shall be verified by an external auditing company and in a standard electronic format that simplifies its inclusion in the Single European Access Point.

What is a Sustainability Plan and why is it Important?

How to make a Sustainability Plan step by step?

Step 1.- Initial diagnosis: assessment of environmental risks and opportunities for improvement.

Step 2.- Define Objectives and Action Plan

What is a Sustainability Plan and why is it Important?

Step 4.- Definition of Key Indicators for each Objective

- *They strengthen the strategies according to results.*
- *Starting value and value to be achieved*
- *Timeframe to achieve objectives.*
- *most relevant indicators*

What is a Sustainability Plan and why is it Important?

MOST IMPORTANT INDICATORS

Environmental Sustainability

- Measuring the use of resources and raw materials.
- Measurement of the use of harmful substances.
- Use of environmentally friendly products.

Social sustainability

- Measurement of employee opinion.
- Total number of employees in social projects.
- Funds raised for social causes.

Financial sustainability:

- Company balance sheet.
- Share prices.
- Labour risk management.
- Accounting policies.
- Expense liabilities and assets.
- Budget evaluation.

What is a Sustainability Plan and why is it Important?

Step 5.- Implementation

Applying the Sustainability Plan to the daily Micro-SMEs management

Step 6.- Monitoring and Evaluation

CONTENT OF THE SUSTAINABILITY PLAN:

Indicator	
Working Standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Diversity: number of employees ● Working conditions
Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Greenhouse Gas Emissions in the year expressed (in million tonnes) ● Electricity consumption in the year expressed in total (kWh) ● Total water consumption (L/year) ● Recycling:
Providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Proportion of expenditure on local suppliers ● Percentage of suppliers selected according to environmental, social and ethical criteria
Compliance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Number of sanctions received for tax non-compliance ● Number of confirmed cases of corruption and actions taken

Legal and reporting obligations on sustainability for micro-SMEs

PROBLEMATICS	REGULATION
Energy Saving	Directive 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency. Directive 2018/2001 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources. Regulation 2018/1999 on the governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action.
Water Saving	UNE-EN ISO 14046: Water footprint of products, processes and organisations.
Environmental Tags	EMAS REGULATION

Annex: ISO Standards

European-level sustainability certification or advisory bodies and institutions

Standards that allow micro-enterprises to communicate, through an independently certified label, their sustainability efforts.

Declarations of Adherence to an Initiative or Code of Conduct

Some of them are quite widespread and have a good reputation

Pros: Not subject to extensive third-party verification. Easy to implement and low cost

Cons: Usually have limited recognition

European-level sustainability certification or advisory bodies and institutions

The United Nations Global Compact is one of the most widespread initiatives today. It involves incorporating 10 principles of responsible management and the Sustainable Development Goals.

The OECD Guidelines for Multinational Enterprises and the ILO Declaration on Multinational Enterprises are also widely disseminated, but both are developed with multinationals rather than micro-SMEs in mind.

European-level sustainability certification or advisory bodies and institutions

- **Certifiable standards.** Certifiable standards are subject to verification by an independent body of compliance with a number of requirements.

The most important ones

Standards covering the overall management of the company

AA1000

IQNet SR 10 Standard

BCorp Certification

SGE 21 Standard. Ethical and socially responsible management system.

European-level sustainability certification or advisory bodies and institutions

Standards that concern only a specific field of activity

European-level sustainability certification or advisory bodies and institutions

- *Seals associated with products speak of the characteristics of the product or service certified by an independent entity.*

2. Labelling according to ISO standards

Three labelling systems

Type I Ecolabel
(ISO 14024)

Type III Environmental Declarations
construction products

Type II Ecolabel
Environmental self-declarations

3. ECOLABEL

Reliable mark, verified through third party checks, for more than 20 different categories of products and services which are regularly updated.

European-level sustainability certification or advisory bodies and institutions

4. Fairtrade seal Emblem of the international Fairtrade system and the most recognised ethical label worldwide. When you buy products with any of the FAIRTRADE seals, you support farmers and workers to improve their quality of life and that of society as a whole.

The Ecolabel adds value to the competitiveness of companies, large or small, by highlighting the eco-efficiency and environmental excellence of those that obtain it.

5. FSC seal It ensures the responsible sourcing of a wide variety of forest-based products from all over the world, starting with the forest of origin, through all the companies involved in their production and packaging, all the way to the consumer.

European-level sustainability certification or advisory bodies and institutions

7. EU ECO seal

The label is awarded to products and services that have a reduced environmental impact compared to other similar products and services on the market, taking into account their entire life cycle.

6. Environmental Technology Verification (ETV)

A tool that verifies the performance of innovative technologies with an environmental character. Its main objective is to facilitate the market entry of new innovative technologies that have an environmental benefit compared to existing technologies.

"I am pushing young people to be social enterprise entrepreneurs and contribute to the world, rather than just making money. Making money is not fun, contributing and changing the world is much more fun".

Muhammad Yunus. Nobel Peace Prize

03

CASE STUDY

01

Case study 1: VOLCÁN STUDIO

CASE STUDY 1

Case study 1: VOLCÁN STUDIO

Volcan Studio is an architecture, engineering and design studio founded in 2015. Since its beginnings, it understands project management through a global vision where formal, graphic and material creation is nourished by a multidisciplinary approach.

Architecture is at a turning point in its evolution in the Canary Islands. Combining design, functionality and technique, it has a determining impact on the environment in which the company is located.

Therefore, while Volcán Studio is building the urban landscape and renovating the spaces, two key terms emerge: sustainability and accessibility.

CASE STUDY 1

Sustainability is not only about building environmentally friendly buildings, but also about constructions that can last over time, generating a positive impact on their surroundings.

On the other hand, accessibility seeks to make these spaces universal, so that citizens can enjoy them, regardless of their physical or sensory abilities and how these change as the population ages.

Looking into the future, there is a firm commitment towards these two dimensions, which are considered cornerstones in the architectural development of the Canary Islands and the world.

CASE STUDY 1

And not just because they represent the right thing to do in ethical terms, but because they are the answer to the demographic and environmental challenges we will face in the near future.

Volcán Studio believes that the best way to do this is to keep up with the times by incorporating the necessary technology and the necessary knowledge that allows them to move forward on a sustainable and accessible path.

A good example of this is the participation in the "Aje Verde" programme, where they were made aware of the management of materials and the implementation of future legal regulations and national and international quality labels.

CASE STUDY 1

With the aim of advancing along this path and being a meeting point for professionals and knowledge, the initiative "Canarias Arquitectura Sostenible" (Canary Islands Sustainable Architecture) was born, which Volcán Studio joins.

It aims to give visibility to the initiatives arising from the Canary Islands and which are adapted to the particularities and singularities of the territory.

<https://canariasarquitecturasostenible.com/volcanstudio.com>

"Sustainable leadership reflects an emerging awareness among people who are choosing to live their lives and run their businesses in a way that takes into account their impact on the planet, society and the health of local and global economies".

Mary A. Ferdig
International Leadership and Develop

04

ASSESSMENT

Q1

The Sustainability Plan

- A. Is a sustainability policy document not subject to the SDGs 2030, sufficient to comply with the regulations and government guidelines of each country.
- B. It is a guide of clear, measurable and realistic objectives to improve the sustainability of the organisation aligned with the SDG 2030.
- C. It is a document designed under the guidelines of the company without being aligned with any European and national regulations.

Q2

The Sustainability Plan should involve

- A. Only the management team.
- B. All employees, managers, customers, suppliers and investors.
- C. Only persons (internal and external) designated by management.

Q3

When will sustainability reporting be mandatory for micro-enterprises?

- A. From 2027 but they can opt out until 1 January 2028.
- B. From 1 January 2025.
- C. No obligation has yet been established in time.

Q4

The sustainability report shall be verified

- A. By an external auditing company without being subject to a standard template.
- B. Not required to be verified.
- C. By an external auditing company and in a standard electronic format that simplifies its inclusion in the Single European Access Point.

Q5

In order to monitor compliance with the Sustainability Plan, it is essential to:

- A. Carry out periodic evaluation, monitoring and control actions.
- B. Design, implement and analyse a system of indicators that, within the framework of a scorecard, provides information on the evolution by objectives and deviations with respect to the estimated value.
- C. All are correct.

Answer Key

Q1: B

Q2: B

Q3: A

Q4: C

Q5: C

"What we do today affects future generations".

Jane GoodAll
United Nations Messenger of Peace

05

KEY TERMS AND DEFINITIONS

-
- **Corporate Social Responsibility/Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR/CSR):** Business principle that seeks to balance business objectives such as productivity and profitability without forgetting ethical and legal principles.
 - **ESG criteria:** They refer to Environmental, Social and Governance factors that are taken into account when investing in a company. ESG stands for "environmental, social and governance".

- ***Environmental Footprint:*** The Environmental Footprint evaluates the environmental impacts of a product or service, based on a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), which is done according to international ISO standards (ISO 14040 and ISO 14044).
- ***Non-Financial Information:*** Sustainability Report: Micro-SME management report providing information on environmental, personnel, human rights, due diligence and sustainability issues.

- **European Ecolabel (EEE):** Certification scheme managed by the EU Ecolabel Committee. It is awarded when products meet ecological and performance criteria.
- **Circular Economy:** A model of production and consumption that involves reducing the waste of resources. It extends the life cycle of products.
- **Climate Neutrality:** Consists of offsetting greenhouse emissions with processes that fix atmospheric carbon.

"Where there is a tree to plant, you plant it; where there is wrong to be righted, you mend it; where there is an effort that everyone else shirks, you do it.

Be the one who moves the stone out of the way".

Gabriela Mistral
Nobel Prize in Literature

06

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REFERENCES

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- www.wtwco.com
- www.redeuroparc.org

"Think globally, act locally".

Jacques Ellul. Philosopher

07

Exhibit: ISO Standards

Annex: Outline of ISO standards

Emissions and carbon footprint	14064-1 14064-2 14064-3 14065 14066 14067	Quantification and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions and removals
Energy Savings	50001 50002 50003 50004 50006 50015	Energy management systems and energy audits
Water Savings	14046	Water footprint of products, processes and organisations.
Environmental Labels	14001	Environmental management system in the company
	14025 14020	TYPE III environmental labels and declarations
	14020	Environmental Labels: General Principles
	14054	Environmental self-declarations. Type II environmental labelling.
	14024	Type I environmental label
	14040 14044	Product life cycle analysis
Wood Sector	9001	Traceability of Wood Products
Corporate Social Responsibility	26000	It is a guide. Not certifiable. Human Rights.

Thank You
Any questions?

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